

Preparation of YAG glass from glass microspheres

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ABSTRACT

A glass, whether in bulk, fibre, or film form, is a non-crystalline solid (NCS) which undergoes a glass transition, to which is associated a glass transition temperature, T_g . In principle, any substance can be vitrified by quenching it from the liquid state, while preventing crystallization, into a solid glass, with the melt structure becoming “frozen” below T_g [1].

In this work, we present our recent research on preparation of bulk YAG glass from YAG glass microspheres. Sol-gel process's (Pechini method) prepared YAG powder was fed into a high temperature methane-oxygen flame (estimated temperature 2800 °C), where the particles melted and YAG glass microspheres were formed. Molten droplets were quenched at the estimated cooling rate 1000 °C/min by spraying them with deionized water to prevent crystallization, and the formed glass microspheres were collected. Viscous flow sintering of YAG glass microspheres were then used to prepare bulk YAG glass in hot press. This is a well-known method in which free surfaces are eliminated by viscous flow at temperatures above T_g . However, many quenched glasses crystallize rapidly at temperatures T_x when the supplied thermal energy mobilizes the structure and the latent heat previously trapped during quenching is released [2]. Crystallization can therefore be observed even during hot-pressing (Fig. 1) by changing of the heating rate slope (measured by thermocouple placed beneath the sample). When crystallization occurs dilatation of the sample stops within few seconds. Which means the amount of residual glass in the sample is so low that elimination of free surfaces by viscous flow is not possible anymore.

Figure 1: Dilatation of YAG sample during hot-pressing as a function of time and changing of sample's temperature vs time.

The working temperature of such glasses is thus restricted to be between T_g and T_x so called kinetic window [2]. According to DSC measurements (Fig. 2) between T_g inflection and T_x onset is 24 °C at the heating rate 5 °C/min. Additionally, during experiment we have to take into account the heat capacity of the carbon die. Therefore, experiments were planned according to dilatation data from hot-press (Fig. 2.)

Fig. 2.: Dilatation of YAG sample during hot-pressing as a function of time and changing of sample's temperature vs time.

Careful optimisation of the sintering conditions lead to the YAG bulk glass/ceramic with the relative density over 99 % with 6 wt. % of crystalline phase.

Keywords: DSC, XRD, YAG.

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